

Original Research Article

Impact of Internal Work Environment on Employees' Productivity in Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa. A Subsidiary of Flour Mills of Nigeria Plc

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Abstract

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Employees' performance is imperative for organizational outcomes and success. Many factors influence employee performance and workplace environment factors stand out as the key determinants of performance. This study aimed to examine the impact of internal work environment on employees' productivity in golden penny rice limited, Apapa. a subsidiary of flour mills of Nigeria plc. The effect of physical workplace factors on employees' productivity error rate, the effect of psychosocial workplace factors on employees' productivity output, and analyze the effect of work-life balance factors on employees' productivity, customers' satisfaction, or complaints handling. Elton Mayo's Hawthorne Effect Theory and Affective Events Theory were adopted for this work. The research adopted a survey research design. The targeted population comprised the employees of Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa. The sample size of the study is 150. The study found that the empirical examination of the hypotheses developed from the conceptual framework presented in this study reveals a mixed set of results. The study recommended that Employee performance should be given serious attention by the firms. Since the work environment is at the core of influencing employees' performance, these organizations should work hard at availing every needed resource in making sure that the work environment supports their employee performance. In addition, incentives play fundamental roles in employees' commitment. Therefore, management should be consistent in giving incentives to workers that desire them on merit grounds. The nature of compensation should be commensurate with what had been delivered by the employee respectively.

Keywords: Employee, Performance, Productivity, Organization, Work-Place

INTRODUCTION

Environment literally means surroundings and all those things that impact human beings during their lifetime are collectively known as environment. Workplace environment is the sum of the interrelationships that exist within the employees and the environment in which they work. According to Heath (2006), this environment involves the physical location as well as the immediate

surroundings, behavioral procedures, policies, rules, culture, resources, working relationships, work location, all of which influence the ways employees perform their work. The quality of the workplace environment impacts on employees' performance and subsequently influences the organization competitiveness. An effective workplace environment management entails making add work

environment attractive, comfortable, satisfactory and motivating to employees so as to give employees a sense of pride and purpose in what they do (Humphries, 2005). Employees will and are always contented when they feel their immediate environment; both physical sensations and emotional states are in tandem with their obligations (Farh, 2012) and how well employees connect with their organization's immediate workplace environment, influences to a great extent their error rate levels, efficiency and innovativeness, collaboration with other employees, absenteeism and, ultimately their retention (Leblebici, 2012)

The type of workplace environment in which employees operate determines whether or not such organizations will prosper (Chandrasekhar, 2011). Physical workplace environment contextualizes the office layout and design while psychosocial factors include working condition, role congruency and social support from supervisors. Policies encompass employment conditions of employees derived from industrial instruments and agreements negotiated with employees and unions, along with our human resources policies. Employees spend fifty percent of their lives within indoor environments, which greatly influence their performance capabilities. Better physical workplace environment will boost employees' performance and ultimately improve their productivity.

A healthy workplace environment makes good business sense and is characterized by respect that supports employee engagement and creates a high-performance culture that encourages innovation and creativity. Organizations deemed as a positive place to work will more likely have a competitive edge since they are in a better position to attract and retain highly skilled employees. This is a significant consideration in the current tight labour market. A positive workplace environment is likely to result in less employee turnover, fewer cases of fraud, better safety practices, easier to attract and retain qualified employees and improved employees' wellbeing (Cunnen, 2006).

Employee performance is the combined result of effort, ability, and perception of tasks (Platt, 2010). Employees' performance is imperative for organizational outcomes and success. Many factors influence employee performance and workplace environment factors stand out as the key determinants of performance. It is the key multi character factor intended to attain outcomes and has a major connection with planned objectives of the organization (Sabir, 2012).

Today's work environment is different, diverse and constantly changing. The typical employer/employee relationship of old has been turned upside down. Workers are living in a growing economy and have almost limitless job opportunities. This combination of factors has created an environment where the business needs its employees more than the employees need the business. In effort to motivate workers, firms have put into practice a number

of activities such as performance-based pay, employee involvement, recruiting agreements, practices to help balance work and family life as well as various forms of information sharing. In addition to motivation, workers need the skills and the ability to do their job effectively. It is the quality of the employees' work environment that most impacts on the level of employees' motivation and subsequent performance. How well employees engage with the organization, especially with their immediate environment, influences to a great extent their error rate, level of uniqueness and collaboration with other employees, absenteeism and ultimately how long they stay in the job. Comfortable office design motivates the employees and increases their performance to a large extent.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective is to examine the impact of add work environment on employees' productivity in Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa a subsidiary of Flour Mills of Nigeria Plc. The following are the specific objectives:

To assess the effect of physical workplace factors on employees' productivity error rate

To examine the effect of psychosocial workplace factors on employees' productivity output.

To analyze the effect of work life balance factors on employees' productivity, customers' satisfaction or complaints handling.

The following research questions will be considered in the study to have the objectives established.

What are the effects of physical workplace factors on employees' productivity?

What are the effects of psychosocial workplace factors on employees' productivity?

What are the effects of work life balance factors on employees' productivity?

Statement of Research Hypotheses

For analyzing the data, the following hypotheses would be tested:

Hypothesis I

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between physical workplace factors and employees' productivity

H₁₁: There is a significant relationship between physical workplace factors and employees' productivity

Hypothesis II

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

psychosocial workplace factors and employees' productivity

H₁₂: There is a significant relationship between psychosocial workplace factors and employees' productivity

Hypothesis III

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between work life balance factors and employees' productivity

H₁₃: There is a significant relationship between work life balance and employees' productivity

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The independent variables are the physical factors, psychosocial factors and work life balance factors. These variables are expected to influence the dependent variables being employee level of productivity in Golden Penny Rice Limited. Figure 1

Independent Variable

Physical Factors of the Workplace Environment

The ability of the physical workplace environment to

influence behaviours and to create an image is particularly apparent for service businesses such as banks. The physical environment includes components of the tangible workplace environment that comprise spatial layout and functionality of the surroundings.

In a broader perspective, the physical workplace environment; include but not limited to the comfort level, ventilation, heating, natural lighting and artificial lighting. According to Temessek, (2009) the above features assist on the functional and aesthetic side, the décor, and design of the workplace environment that ultimately helps improve the employees experience and necessitate better performance.

Office layout and design impressions suggest that certain dimension serves a symbolic function by connoting meanings and images about organizations and further how their employees are to be engaged.

Psychosocial Factors Affecting Employees' Productivity

The psychosocial factor of the work environment is generally considered to be one of the most important issues in contemporary and future societies. They refer to the interactions between the environment and working conditions, organizational conditions, functions and content of the work, effort, workers' individual characteristics and those of members of their families (Vischer, 2008). Therefore, the nature of the psychosocial factors is complex, covering issues relating to the workers, general environment and work.

Noe (2008) defines employee workplace welfare in

terms of six key areas: a manageable workload; some personal control over the job; support from colleagues and supervisors; positive relationships at work; a reasonably clear role; and a sense of control or involvement in changes at the workplace. Individual association with the working environment is important as they impact upon the ability of the individual to take control of their work and the level of stress they experience within the workplace.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Elton Mayo's Hawthorne Effect

Hawthorne set the individual in a social context, establishing that the effectiveness of employees is influenced by their surroundings and by the people that they are working with as much as by their own innate capacities. The original purpose of the experiments was to study the effects of physical conditions on productivity and performance. In addition, the aptitudes of individuals are imperfect predictors of job performance, but the amount produced is strongly influenced by social variables. The studies also showed that the relations that supervisors develop with workers tend to influence the way the workers carry out directives. The theory is relevant to this study since it helps identify the physical environmental variables in the environments which relate with employees' commitment.

Affective Events Theory

Affective events theory (AET) is a model developed by organizational psychologists Howard M. Weiss (Purdue University) and Russell Cropanzano (University of Colorado) to explain how emotions and moods influence employee commitment and job satisfaction. The model explains the linkages between employees' internal influences (for example, cognitions, emotions, mental states) and their reactions to incidents that occur in their work environment that affect their performance, organisational effectiveness and job satisfaction. The theory proposes that affective work behaviours are explained by employee mood and emotions, while cognitive-based behaviours are the best predictors of job satisfaction. The theory proposes that positive-inducing (for example, uplifts) as well as negative-inducing (for example, hassles) emotional incidents at work are distinguishable and have a significant psychological effect upon workers' job satisfaction. This results in lasting internal (for example, cognition, emotions, mental states) and external affective reactions exhibited through job performance, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment. The Affective Events Theory explains the link between employees' internal influences and their

reactions to incidents that occur in their work environment that affect their performance, organisational commitment and job satisfaction (Phua, 2012). It proposes that positive inducing as well as negative emotional incidents at work have significant psychological effects on employees' job satisfaction. The impact results into lasting reactions exhibited through job satisfaction, organisational commitment and job performance. This theory confirms the fact that working conditions influence employee commitment.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study was the survey research design to assess the relationship between work environment and employees' productivity in Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa. This is therefore quantitative in outlook. This design was selected because Robson (2005) explained that a survey research comprises a cross-sectional design in relation to which data are collected predominantly by questionnaire or by structured interview on more than one case (usually quite a lot more than one) and at a single point in time in order to collect a body of quantitative or quantifiable data in connection with two or more variables (usually many, more than two) which are then examined to detect patterns of association.

Population of the Study

The population of this research comprised all the employees of Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa. The research work will focus on Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa having staff strength of 300 - 400 employees as reported in the annual reports 2019 were used as the case study.

Sample Techniques and Sample Size

Stratified random sampling was used to select the respondents for this research in order to divide the entire population into homogeneous groups called strata (plural for stratum). For this study, the population is divided to the number of departments (Logistics, Sales and Market, Administrative, Finance, Procurement, and Risk and Quality Control) in Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa and a random sampling was carried out on staff in each department to represent the population. This is used because it ensured that all the strata of the population were fairly represented and all cases within each stratum had equal chance of being selected. This made it possible to answer the research questions and achieve the objectives of the study.

A sample is referred to as the percentage or fraction of

Table 1. Provide table legend

Physical Environment		SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Std Dev
The furniture I use is comfortable, flexible to adjust, easy to rearrange or reorganize	Frequency	32	58	21	4	5	120	2.1	0.9736
	%	26.7	48.3	17.5	3.3	4.2	100		
My workplace provides an undisturbed environment without any noise that gives me alone time to perform my duties.	Frequency	42	17	31	12	18	120	2.5583	1.43659
	%	35	14.2	25.8	10	15	100		
A better work environment (spacious office, enough lighting etc.) will make me perform better at my job.	Frequency	49	45	14	11	1	120	1.9167	0.98376
	%	40.8	37.5	11.7	9.2	0.8	100		
The room or office I operate from is well illuminated	Frequency	66	40	3	10	1	120	1.6667	0.93784
	%	55	33.3	2.5	8.3	0.8	100		
The temperatures in the room or office I operate from is appropriate	Frequency	36	53	7	14	10	120	2.2417	1.23667
	%	30	44.2	5.8	11.7	8.3	100		

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Keywords: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

the population that answers the research question. The size of the sample is largely determined by calculating what could be achieved with the resources available during the limited duration of the study. Since sampling is a subset of the population of interest to the researcher, the sample for the study was 150 employees of Golden Penny Rice Limited, Apapa.

RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis of Data

The researcher presents the descriptive analysis of variables to answer the research questions. In the descriptive analysis, an independent variable was analyzed. For interpretation, Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD). The detailed results of the analyses are arranged in Table 1.

Table 1 reveals that 75% agreed, 17.5% undecided and 7.5% disagreed that participants the furniture they use is comfortable, flexible to adjust, easy to rearrange or reorganize. Having a standard deviation of 0.9736 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.1. Thus, it vividly indicates truly that the respondent agreed that physical environment with good furniture use enhanced their work productivity. 49.2% agreed, 25.8% undecided and 25% disagreed that their workplace provides an undisturbed environment without any noise that gives me alone time to perform my duties. Having a standard deviation of 1.43659 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.5583. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that there is a conducive environment to work which impact on their productivity level. 78.3% agreed, 11.7% undecided and

10% disagreed that there is a better work environment (spacious office, enough lighting etc.) which makes them perform better at my job. Having a standard deviation of 0.98376 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 1.9167. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that the participants always want a better work environment so as to boost their work performance. 83.3% agreed, 2.5% undecided and 14.2% disagreed that the room or office they operate from is well illuminated. Having a standard deviation of 0.93784 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 1.6667. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that the respondent agreed that the work environment is well conducive and enables them work efficiently. The above question reveals that 74.2% agreed, 5.8% undecided and 20% disagreed that the temperatures in the room or office they operate from is appropriate. Having a standard deviation of 1.23667 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.2417. Thus, it vividly indicates that the respondent agreed that the work environment is suitable to work comfortably.

Table 2 reveals that 73.3% agreed, 10.8% undecided and 15.9% disagreed that they frequently meet with their supervisor about their personal development. Having a standard deviation of 1.17797 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.125. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that the respondent agreed that there is room for personal development and interpersonal relationship which boosts their work performance. 70.8% agreed, 7.5% undecided and 21.7% disagreed that managers inform employees about important decisions, changes, or plans for the future. Having a standard deviation of 1.47051 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.175. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that the respondent agreed that the

Table 2. Provide table legend

Psychosocial Environment		SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Std Dev
I frequently meet with my supervisor about my personal development	Frequency	43	45	13	12	7	120	2.125	1.17797
	%	35.8	37.5	10.8	10	5.8	100		
Managers inform employees about important decisions, changes, or plans for the future	Frequency	58	27	9	8	18	120	2.175	1.47051
	%	48.3	22.5	7.5	6.7	15	100		
I can rely on my supervisor/line manager to help me out with a work problem	Frequency	48	15	11	29	17	120	2.6	1.54702
	%	40	12.5	9.2	24.2	14.2	100		
I am able to contact senior management or work hand in hand with my superior at the workplace.	Frequency	39	43	17	14	7	120	2.225	1.19144
	%	32.5	35.8	14.2	11.7	5.8	100		
Senior management gives staff a clear picture of the direction in which the organization is headed hence motivating me to work	Frequency	34	39	12	19	16	120	2.5333	1.39587
	%	28.3	32.5	10	15.8	13.3	100		

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Keywords: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

management carries their staff along on decisions and helps to boost the level of confidence to put in their best in the work they do. 52.5% agreed, 9.2% undecided and 56.7% disagreed that they can rely on their supervisor/line manager to help them out with a work problem. Having a standard deviation of 1.54702 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.6. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that the respondent did not fully agree that they solely depend on their superior to resolve work problem. 68.3% agreed, 14.2% undecided and 17.5% disagreed that they are able to contact senior management or work hand in hand with their superior at the workplace. Having a standard deviation of 1.19144 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.225. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that the respondents have a sound relationship with their senior and helps to boost their morale towards work. The above question reveals that 60.8% agreed, 10% undecided and 29.2% disagreed that senior management gives staff a clear picture of the direction in which the organization is headed hence motivating them to work. Having a standard deviation of 1.39587 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.5333. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly the respondents are fully detailed on the future view of the company and helps to motivate them to work well.

Table 3 reveals that 57.5% agreed, 15% undecided and 27.5% disagreed that due to work-related duties, I keep on making changes to my plans for family activities. Having a standard deviation of 1.36992 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 2.575. Thus, it vividly indicates that the respondents are

fully engaged with work and tend to have work stress which would affect their work performance as there is effective work life balance. 41.7% agreed, 17.5% undecided and 40.8% disagreed that the demands of their work interfere with their home and family life. Having a standard deviation of 1.40786 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean of 3.0333. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly that the respondents have issues with balancing work and personal life which tells on their level of productivity. 68.3% agreed, 13.3% undecided and 18.4% disagreed that the amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfill family responsibilities. Having a standard deviation of 1.19757 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean 2.1667. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly the respondents are fully overwhelmed with their job function hence, no effective work life balance to manage work and family responsibilities. 63.4% agreed, 19.2% undecided and 17.4% disagreed that my organization provides flexi-time to be able to balance my work and personal life. Having a standard deviation of 1.11367 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean 2.3083. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly the company provides work life balance to their employees. 59.1% agreed, 21.7% undecided and 19.2% disagreed that their organization recognizes the need for leave in order to give employees time off work to relax and attend to personal issues. Having a standard deviation of 1.25354 which indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean 2.4083. Thus, it vividly indicates that truly the respondents have the opportunity to go on vacation to attend to personal issues.

Table 3. Provide table legend

Work Life Balance		SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Std Dev
Due to work-related duties, I keep on making changes to my plans for family activities	Frequency	29	41	18	15	17	120	2.575	1.36992
	%	23.3	34.2	15	12.5	14.2	100		
The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life	Frequency	18	33	21	22	26	120	3.0333	1.40786
	%	14.2	27.5	17.5	18.3	21.7	99		
The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfill family responsibilities	Frequency	45	37	16	17	5	120	2.1667	1.19757
	%	37.5	30.8	13.3	14.2	4.2	100		
My organization provides flexi- time to be able to balance my work and personal life.	Frequency	32	44	23	17	4	120	2.3083	1.11367
	%	26.7	36.7	19.2	14.2	3.3	100		
My organization recognizes the need for leave in order to give employees time off work to relax and attend to personal issues.	Frequency	34	37	26	12	11	120	2.4083	1.25354
	%	28.3	30.8	21.7	10	9.2	100		

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Keywords: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

Table 4. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	1.000	.00000	1.000	.	3	116 ^a	.

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Life Balance, Physical Environment, Psychosocial Environment

Table 5. ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5873.867	3	1957.956	.000 ^b
	Residual	.000	116	.000	
	Total	5873.867	119		

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Life Balance, Physical Environment, Psychosocial Environment

Instrument Validation and Reliability

Therefore, the questions are Valid.

Validity Testing

The purpose of validity testing is to know how far the instruments measured correctly and accurately. Validity testing use regression analysis, with the criteria of acceptance as the following: The item of questionnaire is valid if $r_{\text{statistic}}$ higher than critical value at degree of freedom 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$). Tables 4-6

The Validity rule says that the question is valid when the $r_{\text{statistic}}$ higher than critical value at degree of freedom 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$). For the Budgeting the $r_{\text{statistic}}$ is **1.000^a** which is higher than the critical value ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Reliability Testing

The purpose of reliability testing is to examine the consistency of the data. In this research the reliability is measured by an internal consistency approach that is the concept stressing on the consistency between items in the questionnaires. A construct or variable is reliable if the Croanbach's Alpha is more than 0.6 (Ghazali, 2006). Tables 7-9

In table 7 below, the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.707 which is greater than 0.6, we can say that these

Table 6. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.68E-15	0		.	.	0	0
	Physical Environment	1	0	0.482	.	.	1	1
	Psychosocial Environment	1	0	0.533	.	.	1	1
	Work Life Balance	1	0	0.604	.	.	1	1

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity

Table 7. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.707	4

Table 8. Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Physical Environment	10.4833	3.38554	120
Psychosocial Environment	11.6583	3.74277	120
Work Life Balance	12.4917	4.24065	120
Employees' Productivity	34.6333	7.02568	120

Table 9. Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	17.317	10.483	34.633	24.150	3.304	133.953	4
Item Variances	23.203	11.462	49.360	37.898	4.306	311.281	4

variables are reliable for the research work.

Reject Ho: $\alpha > p\text{-value}$
Accept Ho: $\alpha < p\text{-value}$

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis I

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between physical workplace factors and employees' productivity

H₁₂: There is a significant relationship between physical workplace factors and employees' productivity
 Table 10

Decision Rule

Reject Ho; if the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) is greater than the p-value

Using the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), degrees of freedom (118), p-value is 0.000^b. (i.e. $P < 0.05$). The above result shows that the p-value is less than the level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected; it then means that there is a significant relationship between physical workplace factors and employees' productivity.

Hypothesis II

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between psychosocial workplace factors and employees' productivity

H₁₂: There is a significant relationship between psychosocial workplace factors and employees' productivity. Table 11

Table 10. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.578 ^a	.335	.329	5.75528	.335	59.334	1	118 ^a	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physical Environment

Table 11. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1965.328	1	1965.328	59.334	.000 ^b
	Residual	3908.538	118	33.123		
	Total	5873.867	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Physical Environment

Table 12. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
				Beta				
1	(Constant)	22.049	1.716		12.849	.000	18.651	25.448
	Physical Environment	1.200	.156	.578	7.703	.000	.892	1.509

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity

Table 13. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.646 ^a	.417	.412	5.38655	.417	84.443	1	118 ^a	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Psychosocial Environment

Decision Rule

Reject H₀; if the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) is greater than the p-value

Reject H₀: $\alpha > p\text{-value}$
Accept H₀: $\alpha < p\text{-value}$

Using the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), degrees of freedom (118), p-value is 0.000^b. (i.e. $P < 0.05$). The above result shows that the p-value is less than the level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected; it then means that there is a significant relationship between psychosocial workplace factors and employees' productivity.

Hypothesis III

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between work

life balance factors and employees' productivity

H₁₃: There is a significant relationship between work life balance and employees' productivity Table 12

Decision Rule

Reject H₀; if the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) is greater than the p-value

Reject H₀: $\alpha > p\text{-value}$
Accept H₀: $\alpha < p\text{-value}$

Using the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), degrees of freedom (118), p-value is 0.000^b. (i.e. $P < 0.05$). The above result shows that the p-value is less than the level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected; it then means that there is a significant relationship between work life balance and employees' productivity. Table 13-18

Table 14. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2450.106	1	2450.106	84.443	.000 ^b
	Residual	3423.761	118	29.015		
	Total	5873.867	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Psychosocial Environment

Table 15. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	20.499	1.615		12.695	.000	17.302	23.697
	Psychosocial Environment	1.212	.132	.646	9.189	.000	.951	1.474

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity

Table 16. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.625 ^a	.391	.385	5.50802	.391	75.612	1	118 ^a	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Life Balance

Table 17. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2293.949	1	2293.949	75.612	.000 ^b
	Residual	3579.918	118	30.338		
	Total	5873.867	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Life Balance

Table 18. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	21.700	1.570		13.821	.000	18.591	24.809
	Work Life Balance	1.035	.119	.625	8.696	.000	.800	1.271

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Productivity

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The empirical examination of the hypothesis developed from the conceptual framework presented in this study reveals a mixed set of results.

CONCLUSION

The most important resource for an organization is the human resources who are the employees. They make sufficient contributions to an organization; attention

should therefore be paid to them. Organizations can only realize their goals and objectives through its employees' performance. Employees will strive to perform when they feel that their immediate environment state corresponds with their obligations. The type of work environment in which they operate will determine whether they perform or not, it's through their performance that organizational performance can be realized. The workplace conditions will determine the employees' comfort to work and boost their performance.

From the study findings, it can be concluded that for an organization to have a competitive edge over others, it must provide a positive work environment in which all factors that influence employee performance are in tandem with their obligation. Many factors affect employee performance that managers/supervisors need to be aware of and should work to improve at all times. It was determined that the employees understood their roles and responsibilities and were performing a wide range of activities to fulfill various obligations expected of them. Hence, based on these findings, the study concludes that all of them were important variables in the study beginning with the most crucial which in this case was psychosocial aspects.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are offered as a way of enhancing productivity in an organization:

The firms should ensure that the workplace environment is comfortable enough to support employee performance by improving the working conditions. Improving the working environment will increase employee performance. When the work environmental supports are sound, employees are better equipped to do what is expected of them. Through this, they will achieve organizational goals.

Employee performance should be given serious attention by the firms. Since the work environment is at the core of influencing employees' performance, these organizations should work hard at availing every needed resource in making sure that the work environment supports their employee performance.

Organizations should incorporate a feedback approach into its system. This will enable them to assess useful information that can be used to solve or analyses current and future problems. Issues that are relevant to the workplace, particularly in the area of employees' inefficiency and low productivity.

Feedback is a management tools that reveals to employees his or her level of commitment to responsibilities, this recommendation will encourage potential and visionary employees to apply more effort that will facilitate them to add values to the company and peradventure enable organizations to play her basic roles in economic development.

Workplace environmental factors are antidotes that ammonize employee with their environment. In that regard, it must be meticulously and systematically

integrated and harness by managements to ascertain their specific objectives and compete favorably in global market.

In addition, incentives play fundamental roles in employees' commitment. Therefore, management should be consistent in giving incentives to workers that desire it on merit ground. The nature of compensation should commensurate with what had been delivered by the employee respectively.

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